

Are Air Travel Restrictions Necessary to Address Climate Change?

Climate change is arguably one of the most urgent challenges we face in the 21st century, affecting all parts of life, from the environment to economies to human health. Air travel is one of the many contributors to this issue, affecting nearly 4% of all greenhouse gas emissions, with scientists estimating it to increase over the years due to a spike in flight demand.¹ Air transport enables international connectivity, drives economic growth, supports essential services, and is a seamless part of the modern world. Yet the consistent rise of the problem of global climate change is causing disastrous effects around the world, such as sea-level rise, weather-related dangers, and loss of biodiversity, threatening the world to an unprecedented extent. So then, the question arises: are air travel restrictions necessary to address climate change? I will examine this question from two conflicting perspectives, analysing their arguments for and against the research question to form a well-balanced judgment and conclusion.

The case for economic growth is well presented by Haldane Dodd in his article “Aviation: Benefits Beyond Borders” (2024). His report presents the tremendous input of the global aviation industry to the economy, creating over 86.5 million jobs both directly and indirectly, and a global economic contribution of \$4.1 trillion.² This shows the large role that the aviation sector plays in economic growth worldwide. Further, the contribution of the airline industry to economic growth is supported in the research conducted by Harvard researchers, titled “Air Transportation and Regional Economic Development: A Case Study for the New Airport in South Albania.” The research investigates the economic effects of airport development, particularly how the creation of a new airport influences regional economic development. The study establishes that these infrastructure projects create immense employment opportunities and attract foreign investment. It is confirmed that new businesses and overseas franchises move to areas with a high quality of air service since it supports efficient trade and mobility of labour. This increases business operations, supports business partnerships and improves access to international markets. Besides business and employment expansion, studies educate us that aviation contributes to economic stability by being based on tourism, a chief source of income for countries.³ Going further, to make the argument more compelling, an

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<https://news.mongabay.com/2022/04/how-much-does-air-travel-warm-the-planet-new-study-gives-a-figure/>

2 https://aviationbenefits.org/media/e5ynn4x0/abbb2024_full_report.pdf

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<https://growthlab.hks.harvard.edu/files/growthlab/files/2020-06-cid-fellows-wp-127-albania-air-transport.pdf>

Oxford Economics study titled ‘Economic Benefits from Air Transport in the UK’ adds extra research done in the UK. In the UK alone, the airline industry adds a total of £52 billion to the UK GDP, which is approximately 3.4% of its entire GDP, as well as employing 961,000 jobs, illustrating how, in just one country, it brings that amount of value.⁴ Therefore, it is clear that the major impact air travel has on the economy is prominent, which makes it a positive side for the argument, strengthening the opinion that air travel restrictions are not necessary to address climate change. I generally find all three documents to be reliable sources of information. Haldane Dodd, for example, has over 16 years of experience with the Air Transportation Action Group and appears to be a specialist in their field. The article by Oxford Economics was published by a group associated with Oxford University, which suggests that individuals with strong academic backgrounds likely wrote it. Finally, the other article is written by fellow Harvard scientist Shreyas Gadgin Matha, who specialises in economic research and is paired up with Harvard associates Patricio Goldstein and Jessie Lu. While institutional affiliation does not in itself make someone credible, the

In addition, air transport has an important function in rural and distant communities to obtain basic services such as emergency assistance, education, and healthcare. In rural communities, air transport is especially beneficial to carry clinical health care during emergency cases, especially for trauma, cardiac, neonatal, and respiratory conditions. Concrete examples of how air transport has saved lives in rural communities are shown in the research report ‘Functions and Benefits of Rural Airports in Washington’ by Jon Newkirk. The report offers several stories of how a single aeroplane was vital in saving lives, for instance, a mother experiencing severe pregnancy complications in her seventh month was flown to another town in a short plane ride, saving both her and her child, a journey that would have otherwise taken 3.5 hours by car.⁵ Air transportation also offers children access to study abroad and pursue higher education, especially in underdeveloped or isolated areas, where gaining access to quality education and improving living standards is particularly difficult. This is supported by the study ‘Importance of Aviation in Higher Education’ by Gisle Solvoll and Thor-Erik Sandberg Hanssen, which explores the educational benefits of air travel. The article reveals how close a child is to a Higher Education Institution significantly influences whether they pursue further education, something challenging in some regions. In Norway, for example, many high school graduates move to more urbanised areas to attend better institutions. This contributes to Norway having the highest number of flights per

⁴ <https://airlinesuk.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/Oxford-Economics-2014.pdf>

⁵ <https://www.wsdot.wa.gov/research/reports/fullreports/557.1.pdf>

capita in Europe, underlining aviation's key role in accessing education.⁶ I consider these articles trustworthy. The first source was authored by Jon Newkirk and Ken Casavant for the Washington State Department of Transportation Aviation Division—an official government body for aerospace matters, however this was written in 2002, which may be less trustworthy today as it may not account for recent technological advancements, updated emissions data, or evolving climate policies.. The second study was composed by Gisle Solvoll, a professor and author at Nord University, in collaboration with Thor-Erik Sandberg Hanssen, another professor at Nord University. This makes the article reliable. Furthermore, it includes extensive research, with precise statistics, figures, graphs, maps, and equations, enhancing its credibility.

On the other hand, air transport is one of the fastest-growing contributors to climate change and environmental degradation due to its release of significant greenhouse gases. The world has developed at a rapid pace over the past few years, and the consequences of this are already starting to peek through and will impose an even bigger problem in the future. The damage of air transport on the environment is shown in the article 'Exposing the environmental impacts of air transport on the ecological system: empirical evidence from APEC countries' written by Nattapan Kongbuamai. The study highlights the profound danger as commercial aviation released 920 million metric tonnes of CO₂ in 2018, and global aviation emissions are forecast to expand by 322% between 2006 and 2050 due to the vast technological advancements predicted to be made.⁷ The consequences are once more shown on the article 'The Growth in Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Commercial Aviation' which states that the aviation sector accounted for 2.4% total emissions of the world in 2018, which may not seem like a lot, if global commercial aviation had been a country, it would stand in sixth place. Plus, it says that the ratio of carbon dioxide to jet fuel is that for every 1 kilogram of jet fuel, 3.16 kilograms of carbon dioxide is released, showing how negatively aeroplanes affect the environment. Surprisingly, the study provides us with an interesting fact that the white cloud left by an aircraft as it passes by, called contrails, could potentially be more detrimental to global warming as it produces a warming effect of up to 3 times that of CO₂.⁸ Both of these studies shed light on the ongoing problem of climate change and the impact of aviation that adds to that issue. These sources are reliable because one

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<https://nordopen.nord.no/nord-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/2574397/Solvoll.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y>

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[https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(23\)07043-3?_returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2FRetrieve%2Fapi%2FS2405844023070433%3Fshowall%3Dtrue](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(23)07043-3?_returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2FRetrieve%2Fapi%2FS2405844023070433%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)

⁸ https://www.eesi.org/files/IssueBrief_Climate_Impacts_Aviation_2019rev2022.pdf

of them was written by Nattapan Kongbuamai, a professor at a university based in Thailand. On the other hand, there is no clear author written on it, but it is a study released by the Environmental and Energy Study Institute, established in 1984, designed to give reliable information/statistics on anything related to energy. Plus, it is more reliable because the article contains an abundance of sources that were cited.

Furthermore, private flights pose a growing concern in the fight against climate change, as their rapidly increasing use highlights the environmental cost of luxury and convenience in air travel, raising questions about sustainability and social responsibility. In the article 'Private aviation is making a growing contribution to climate change,' it states that there were 25,993 total private jets counted in 2023, and 15.62 Mt of CO₂ was released from them, and almost half of the total flights had a distance of less than 500 km and a whopping 4.7% travelled a distance of less than 50 km.⁹ Specifically for celebrities, it has become an essential part of their life, and it is clearly shown in the case of Taylor Swift, who had the highest carbon footprint among all, showing that the amount of CO₂ released was 8,300 tonnes in 2022, approximately 1,800 times the average annual human emissions—an exceptionally high figure.¹⁰ Cases like these highlight how crucial some air travel restrictions could be in preserving our environment. I also consider these sources to be dependable because the first one was made by Stefan Gössling, who is a well-respected academic who has worked/studied the interrelationship of tourism, transport and sustainability for a quarter of a century, partnered up with other various professors and specialists. The other website is a non-profit watchdog and research organisation that focuses on carbon pricing and advocates for fair and effective climate action.

After considering the arguments of both sides, the argument in favor of 'Are air travel restrictions necessary to solve climate change?' is also strong because there has been more than enough evidence shown, proving the means through which aviation releases a massive amount of greenhouse gases, which directly causes the current crisis of climate change. The argument is an effective counterargument as to why air travel restrictions are essential to slow down the rate of deteriorating the environment.

However, the counterargument for 'Are air travel restrictions necessary to address climate change?' is stronger because a majority of the sources prove that the benefits of aviation outweigh the possible negatives. Such examples include economic assistance, social improvements in people's lives, and

⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-024-01775-z>

¹⁰ <https://carbonmarketwatch.org/2024/02/13/taylor-swift-and-the-top-polluters-department/>

improved living standards. The majority of these sources were written by high-profile individuals, e.g., writers and specialists, and individuals who worked for governmental organisations in connection with the aviation sector.

In conclusion, air travel restrictions are not necessary to address climate change. The argument that it massively promotes substantial growth in a country proves how vital this industry is for everyone. Specific sources show the massive assistance it gives to countries in both highly developed and developing countries, which is backed up by authors who are highly educated in the field of study. On the other hand, the opposing argument uses sources primarily made by non-governmental organisations, which makes it less reliable. The first perspective is consequently the stronger side, which leads to my conclusion, and I have high confidence in this conclusion based on the broad range of evidence shown.

Nonetheless, further research could be done by me to improve the validity of my conclusion, such as taking into account the rapid technological developments in aviation and how efficiently they are working on expanding the use of carbon-zero aeroplanes and similar innovations, which would've given me a better understanding of the perspective. Adding on, I could've included the public opinion and ethics on this debate, whether they agree with commercial flying or are against it. This would widen the social perspective on whether the majority of the population is on board, which could challenge my conclusion and my viewpoint on this topic, 'Are air travel restrictions necessary to address climate change?'

Citations:

1. Benja Faecks, Eleanor Scott. February 13, 2024. "Taylor Swift and the Top Polluters Department", Carbon Market Watch. (Accessed March 3, 2025)
<https://carbonmarketwatch.org/2024/02/13/taylor-swift-and-the-top-polluters-department/>.
2. "Economic Benefits from Air Transport in the UK." Oxford Economics. November 2014 (Accessed February 13, 2025)
<https://airlinesuk.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/Oxford-Economics-2014.pdf>.
3. Gisle Solvoll, and Thor-Erik Sandberg Hanssen. September 2018. "Importance of Aviation in Higher Education." Nord University (Accessed February 24, 2025)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2018.08.001>.
4. Haldane Dodd. December 2024. "Aviation Benefits Beyond Borders." Aviation Benefits. December 2024. (Accessed February 11, 2025)
https://aviationbenefits.org/media/e5ynn4x0/abbb2024_full_report.pdf
5. Jon Newkirk and Ken Casavant. February 25, 2002. "FUNCTIONS and BENEFITS of RURAL AIRPORTS in WASHINGTON." (Accessed February 20, 2025)
<https://www.wsdot.wa.gov/research/reports/fullreports/557.1.pdf>.
6. Liz Kimbrough. April 6, 2022. "How Much Does Air Travel Warm the Planet? New Study Gives a Figure." Mongabay Environmental News. (Accessed February 11, 2025)
<https://news.mongabay.com/2022/04/how-much-does-air-travel-warm-the-planet-new-study-gives-a-figure/>
7. Nattapan Kongbuamai, Ali Hashemizadeh, Virginia Cheung, and Dang Hong Bui. September 2023. "Exposing the Environmental Impacts of Air Transportation on the Ecological System: Empirical Evidence from APEC Countries." Heliyon. (Accessed February 28, 2025)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19835>.
8. Shreyas Gadgin Matha, Patricio Goldstein, and Jessie Lu. June 2020. "Air Transportation and Regional Economic Development: A Case Study for the New Airport in South Albania." (Accessed February 13, 2025)

<https://growthlab.hks.harvard.edu/files/growthlab/files/2020-06-cid-fello ws-wp-127-albania-air-transport.pdf>.

9. Stefan Gössling, Andreas Humpe, and Jorge Cardoso Leitão. November 7, 2024. "Private Aviation Is Making a Growing Contribution to Climate Change." (Accessed March 3, 2025)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01775-z>.
10. "The Growth in Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Commercial Aviation." October 2019. (Accessed March 3, 2025)
https://www.eesi.org/files/IssueBrief_Climate_Impacts_Aviation_2019rev_2022.pdf.